

NEW APPROACHES AND METHODS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE AT SCHOOL

Nematullaeva Muslimakhon Rakhmatullo kizi

Student of the third English faculty, UzSWLU

E-mail: muslimanematullayeva797@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Developing the effectiveness of foreign language teaching has become a topic of the day. Since new approaches and methods play a significant role in boosting education and developing students' language skills, teachers are being required to use them. This article is devoted to considering new approaches and methods used in teaching foreign languages.

Keywords: *Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) approach, Lexical approach, pedagogues, new approach, method, cooperative learning.*

MAKTABDA CHET TILINI O'QITISHNING YANGI YONDASHUVLARI VA USULLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Jamiyatimizda chet tillarini o'qitish samaradorligini oshirish kun mavzusiga aylanib ulgurgan. O'qituvchilardan yangi yondashuv va usullardan foydalanish talab qilinmoqda, chunki ular dars sifatini oshirishda hamda o'quvchilarning til ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Ushbu maqolada chet tillarini o'qitishda foydalanib kelinayotgan yangi yondashuv va metodlar haqida so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: *til o'qitishning kommunikativ (CLT) yondashuvi, Leksik yondashuv, pedagoglar, yangi yondashuv, metod, hamkorlikda o'rganish.*

НОВЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ И МЕТОДЫ ОБУЧЕНИЯ ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ В ШКОЛЕ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Повышение эффективности обучения иностранным языкам стало актуальной темой в нашей обществе. От учителей требуется использование новых подходов и методов, поскольку они играют важную роль в повышении качества уроков и развитии языковых навыков учащихся. В данной статье рассказывается о новых подходах и методах, используемых в обучении иностранным языкам.

Ключевые слова: коммуникативный подход обучения иностранному языку (CLT), лексический подход, педагоги, новый подход, метод, совместное обучение.

INTRODUCTION

The use of many interactive, creative teaching techniques in schools is a defining feature of the growth and accomplishments of national education. Since teaching and learning a foreign language are both regarded as complex processes, teachers should use interactive teaching strategies in their sessions. And that makes it easier for teachers to conduct worthwhile and successful lessons. Integrative methods involve engaging in a certain kind of educational work in the form of activities. Additionally, this kind of instruction aims to assist students in connecting several languages covered in the school curriculum. Furthermore, both globally and in Uzbekistan, the importance and influence of the English language are growing continuously. So, the goal of improved standards in foreign language learning, namely in English, was set by the Presidential Decree titled "On Measures to Promote Foreign Language Learning in the Republic of Uzbekistan to a Fundamentally New Level" in May 2021.

Difference between a method and an approach

Due to the similarities in meaning between these two words, “method” and “approach”, they are frequently used interchangeably. Both are instructional designs that have principles and practices that guide the teaching and learning process.

Moreover, the approach sets the general rule or general principle to make learning possible. Contrarily, a technique is a planned, well-organized, systematic process that is meant to facilitate and improve students’ learning.

METHODS

While conducting this research, qualitative and secondary data analysis methods were used. Numerous methods for teaching languages have been adopted into our educational system. Moreover, an approach is a hypothesis regarding how language instruction should be conducted;

- ◆ A method or methodology outlines how the approach is implemented.
- ◆ Techniques describe specific tasks and activities to practice with the class.

For instance:

- ❖ Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) is a technique based on the notion that language is used for communication.

- ❖ A notional-functional or structural syllabus is the foundation of a CLT technique. The language learner will be placed at the center of either a structural or a notional-functional curriculum, with the primary goal being the advancement of their communicative competence. The selection of classroom exercises will encourage students to interact with one another.
- ❖ Role-playing, dialogues, text ordering, speaking games, and problem-solving exercises are some of the CLT tactics.

The CLT method of teaching languages assumes that the speaker and listener will negotiate meaning because meaning is the primary focus of all communicative activities. Additionally, this method considers every element of language, not only speaking. When the Ministry of Public Education created State Educational Standards towards the end of the 1990s, the CLT technique initially entered into the curriculum in Uzbekistan. The new curriculum's main goal was to improve communicative fluency and move away from grammar-based teaching methods. More than just putting students in pairs or groups to do tasks is needed for CLT approaches to be successfully implemented. Every student in a language class has unique needs, skill levels, and interests. As a result, in CLT, it is crucial to have a variety of assignments that are created to fit the needs and abilities of various pupils. Additionally, encouraging engagement in the classroom helps students feel more comfortable doing so, especially those who are easily intimidated by it. Following are seven helpful hints for using the CLT approach:

- ✚ There should be a lot of communicative student-student activities including pair discussions, role-playing, puzzle-solving, and other cooperative tasks.
- ✚ Activities that involve communication should have a clear scenario or context, the speakers' respective responsibilities, and a communicative purpose.
- ✚ Encourage students to reflect on their language learning progress and set goals for growth. This will help students build metacognitive skills. This promotes a sense of autonomy and responsibility in their learning process.

- ✚ Use the appropriate tools to design and assign speaking-based language learning activities. For instance, modern language teaching software tools can be used, which allows them to practice their spoken English. Software technologies let students listen to their recordings, which facilitates crucial self-evaluation.

The Audiolingual Approach

- The Audiolingual Approach is founded on the structuralist understanding of language and uses stimulus and response as the foundation of its learning theory.
- In audio-lingual lessons, learners get used to complex grammatical structures by listening to the language and responding, which is a rather mechanistic approach. There is no systematic grammar instruction because it often involves memorization of dialogues.
- Techniques to increase the accuracy of language forms and patterns include listening and repeating as well as oral drilling. Teachers may use communicative exercises in later classes.

Dialogues and drills serve as the foundation for audio-lingual classroom activities, as was described above. Dialogue serves as a context and is employed for learning and repetition. The teacher can provide a dialogue first, and then choose some fresh material. The lesson's main emphasis is on vocabulary or particular grammatical constructions. There could be numerous procedures in a typical audiolingual class.

- ✚ Students strive to imitate the pronunciation and intonation of native speakers by listening to dialogue.
- ✚ The dialogue can be changed to suit the interests of the learners. When students speak about their favorite subjects, they are more motivated to participate. Both the teacher and the pupils may apply the same grammar structure they have learned from the dialogue while changing the keywords.

- ✚ Students work through activities based on dialogues in their textbook to improve both their skills (listening, speaking, reading, and writing) and sub-skills (grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation).

CLIL-Content and Language Integrated Learning

- A method known as CLIL combines the study of a particular subject with that of the target language. To reach the learning objectives, learners must engage with the language. In terms of philosophy, its supporters believe that it promotes communication across cultures, meaningful language use, and the growth of practical skills for use in the real world.
- Fluency in the target language is used in this approach, and the activities and content are determined by the subject being taught. Activities frequently combine a variety of task types that are appealing to different ways of learning with all four skills.

Activity types in the CLIL approach:

The methodologies that reflect the mix of communication and skills must be limited if we are to examine teaching practice within this new equation. By restricting, we make clear the practice's limits that can help us do this.

There seem to be four fundamental activity categories in CLIL that can support pupils in thriving despite their comparatively limited linguistic resources. Both basic and secondary school as well as post-compulsory education can use these categories.

- ✚ Peer communication-enhancing activities that integrate conceptual content and communicative proficiency
- ✚ Reading strategy-building exercises (because actual texts are frequently cognitively and linguistically difficult)
- ✚ Exercises that direct students' oral and writing creation (concentrate on production planning - "minimum guarantees")

The Lexical Approach

- A method based on the idea that language is made up of lexical units (chunks, collocations, and fixed phrases). Learning these chunks helps students master grammar, which is important.
- The method focuses on teaching groups of phrase-level, multi-word vocabulary, and linguistic contexts that the student can control via substitutions and adaptations. Numerous common EFL exercises can be modified to do this.
- Techniques could include looking for lexical units in texts, playing collocation matching games, practicing lexical tests and songs, telling stories, employing fixed and semi-fixed phrases in role plays, engaging in activities with de-lexical verbs, and taking a look at concordances.

How to apply the Lexical approach in the classroom

- ✚ Students should be immersed in authentic materials. "Authentic material" refers to exposure to the language as it is used naturally by native speakers. Authentic material differs from tutorials or textbooks written specifically for language learners. Those are designed to be simple. For instance, in video lessons, instructors speak slowly and clearly so that viewers can follow along. Additionally, they provide definitions and phrase samples for each term.
- ✚ They should highlight lexical chunks. Students may initially find it difficult to determine for themselves which words in the sentences come as a group. The teacher's task will be to draw attention to them. On the board highlight or circle them. The teacher should ask the class to repeat them after her or him as he or she says them repeatedly. They should be removed from the rest of the sentence's words. Their meaning should be described to the students.
- ✚ Invest in listening and reading activities. Teachers should give students a lot to read and hear if they want to improve their ability to recognize lexical chunks in the target language. Their ears will acquire used to the rhythm and rhyme of the target language with continued auditory exposure. After reading a lot of

authentic information, the naturally occurring phrases will start to slowly emerge from the page and poke the reader in the eye. (Not literally)

RESULTS

The use of a communicative teaching approach is to produce new, fluent English speakers. It is considered that improving existing teaching methods to enhance students' oral English proficiency is a crucial part of the curriculum. Using the activities that cooperative learning includes helps to promote cooperation and interaction among learners. Both communicative instruction and cooperative learning provide students with important ways of succeeding while learning a foreign language, since by using them, students can be at the center of the learning process. These new approaches and methods aim to develop spoken language and improve the ability to communicate. If communicative methods are used in the education system, students can be more active than they were before during the lesson. An essential side of this method is that real communication situations are created, and there is an opportunity for them to put all the knowledge gained into practice.

Principles	Traditional approaches	CLT
Goals of language teaching	Grammatical competence	Communicative competence
How learners learn a language	Process of mechanical habit formation	Processes of purposeful interaction and collaborative creation of meaning are negotiated.

DISCUSSION

While using the CLT approach, these concerns may be raised:

- Sometimes teachers may struggle with the requirements of CLT, which are considered non-specific.
- Giving up too much control when having a CLT exercise makes teachers worry frequently.
- The majority of students are not confident enough to communicate in a foreign language, so this case may cause obstacles while doing the CLT exercises.
- As CLT is an approach that focuses on the meaning of context, learners may face difficulties related to grammar.

There is an approach that originated in CLT, and it is named Task-based Teaching (TBT). It addresses all of the concerns mentioned above; moreover, it provides teachers with clear instructions on how to get the students to finish the given

task. Pre-task, task and post-task processes provide teachers who were concerned that their classrooms would become chaotic due to a lack of structure in the session with defined stages that establish guidelines and boundaries. Since they own the language and have control over the task response, learners feel more empowered when they complete tasks. Teachers can add a language focus as an optional addition to a work to address any grammar errors that the task highlights, although TBT puts more focus on meaning than form.

CONCLUSION

In the modern teaching approach, the learner is the main focus of curriculum preparation and teaching. In this manner, students actively engage in the entire process to increase their knowledge and develop their skills. Nowadays, attracting students to the class through new methods and approaches is in demand, so a teacher must introduce each language skill in a setting or context that is relevant to the learner. If teachers consistently use one strategy or approach, it may cause confusion and mistakes among the students. Pedagogues should follow a unified approach that encourages them to use all of the available methods, tactics, and techniques to rectify their students' mistakes and also guide them appropriately.

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